

This is the true Queensland:

And this is the border of the truest Queensland:

This place, of the truest Queensland, forever lost to time, yet forever found by time, and that is why, me, Lachlan Madden, live in truest Queensland, the state of the country of Promethia, where I am also lost to time yet forever found by time. And if somewhere on this truest map of Queensland, then literally inside dreams, ever so pictured. The name for this place is Queensland, and that is true, and that is why the truest name for this place specified on the map, is gardenlands.

And this is the layers of the Queensland gardenlands map:

- When the final dreamerless dreamer hidden Queensland gardenlands map, then the final dreamerless dreamer seen Queensland gardenlands map.
- When nameless name of the drugless drug hiddenless hidden Queensland gardenlands map, then the nameless name of the drugless drug seenless seen Queensland gardenlands map.
- When godless god hiddenless hidden Queensland gardenlands map, then godless god seenless seen Queensland gardenlands map.

- When brainless brain hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then brainless brain seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When whimsless whim hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then whimsless whim seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When PointlessPointBlanklessBlankHiddenlessHidden queensland gardenlands map, then PointlessPointBlanklessBlankSeenlessSeen queensland gardenlands map.
- When dreamless dream hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then dreamless dream seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When portalless portal hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then portalless portal seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When matterless matter hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then matterless matter seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When forceless force hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then forceless force seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When mirrorless mirror hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then mirrorless mirror seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When everythingless everything hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then everythingless everything seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When anythingless anything hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then anythingless anything seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When nothingless nothing hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then nothingless nothing seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When somethingless something hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then somethingless something seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When 0th hiddenless hidden winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map, then 0th seenless seen winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map.
- When 1st hiddenless hidden winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map, then 1st seen winner queensland gardenlands map.
- When 2nd hiddenless hidden winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map, then 2nd seenless seen winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map.
- When 3rd hiddenless hidden winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map, then 3rd seenless seen winnerless winner queensland gardenlands map.
- When innerless inner hiddenless hidden innerless inner queensland gardenlands map, then innerless inner seenless seen innerless inner queensland gardenlands map.
- When innerless inner hiddenless hidden middleless middle queensland gardenlands map, then innerless inner seenless seen middleless middle queensland gardenlands map.
- When innerless inner hiddenless hidden outerless outer queensland gardenlands map, then innerless inner seenless seen outerless outer queensland gardenlands map.
- When middleless middle hiddenless hidden innerless inner queensland gardenlands map, then middleless middle seenless seen innerless inner queensland gardenlands map.
- When middleless middle hiddenless hidden middleless middle queensland gardenlands map, then middleless middle seenless seen middleless middle queensland gardenlands map.
- When middleless middle hiddenless hidden outerless outer queensland gardenlands map, then middleless middle seenless seen outerless outer queensland gardenlands map.

- When outerless outer hiddenless hidden innerless inner queensland gardenlands map, then outerless outer seenless sene innerless inner queensland gardenlands map.
- When outerless outer hiddenless hidden middleless middle queensland gardenlands map, then outerless outer seenless seen middleless middle queensland gardenlands map.
- When outerless outer hiddenless hidden outerless outer queensland gardenlands map, then outerless outer seenless seen outerless outer queensland gardenlands map.
- When lastless last finalless final hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then at firstless first finallylless finally seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When insideless inside hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then insideless inside seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When outsideless outside hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then outsideless outside seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When reflectionless reflection hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then reflectionless reflection seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.
- When horrorless horror hiddenless hidden queensland gardenlands map, then horrorless horror seenless seen queensland gardenlands map.

And the spin paradox model that represents by a forcefield of Queensland gardenlands, goes as followed: When Queensland gardenlands dimension, then heaven-time-dimension-force paired with hell-time-dimension-force, and when heaven-time-dimension-force paired with hell-time-dimension-force, then extra dream-time-dimension-force, and when the extra dream-time-dimension-force, then the outcome of nightmare-time-dimension-force, and when the outcome of nightmare-time-dimension-force, then the outcome extra of DeepDream-time-dimension-force, and when the outcome extra of DeepDream-time-dimension-force, then heaven-time-dimension-force paired with hell-time-dimension-force.

Outside the border of gardenlands, is the magical abyss of Ginnungagap, the inlands yet the outlands, of the light void.

And inside the map border of gardenlands, is the magical void, the dark void.

Map base finally set.